

000231 DNS of the Molten Salt Bubble Growth with PSI-BOIL

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With the concurrence of the loss of flow (LOFW) and loss of heat sink (LOHS) accident in the pool type Molten Salt Reactor (MSR), the boiling of the molten salt liquid could occur naturally due to the presence of the volumetric decay heat source inside the salt. To investigate the phase change phenomenon within the MSR channel during the accident, a preliminary study on the molten salt bubble growth is performed with the PSI in-house Computational Fluid Dynamics code PSI-BOIL, which has been extensively applied to the simulation of boiling phenomena in the past. A 1D quasi-static Stefan problem and a spherical symmetric bubble-heating problem are chosen for verifying the PSI-BOIL for problems featuring internal heating. Following the verification, single bubble growth problem with buoyancy and natural convection is considered.

KEYWORDS: *DNS, Bubble Growth, Molten Salt*

Introduction

The high melting and boiling point of molten salt have given a large safety margin for the operation of the MSR. From the safety assessment of MSR, it is understood that the primary method to remove the decay heat from the salt is by natural circulating the salt through the heat exchanger. Based on the design basis accident (DBA) without single failure criteria, the MSR is inherently safe due to the high heat capacity and the large margin to boiling of the salt [1].

The Fukushima accident showed to the whole nuclear community that failures in multiple safety systems could happen at the same time (i.e., external events could disable the whole reactor safety response chain). The safety assessment of the MSR should not only focus in the plant responses during the DBA but also the hypothetical accident with multiple component failures. For example, the concurrent occurrence of the loss of flow (LOF) and loss of heat sink accident (LOHS) could challenge the safety margin of the salt due to the loss of natural circulation (or even only with LOHS alone). The decay heat emitted from the salt could initiate boiling even the salt has a high specific heat capacity. For the extreme case, the MSR may experience the unprotected loss of flow accident (ULOF) with the concurrent loss of heat sink accident; this could lead to vaporization of the salt that is undesirable in terms of reactor safety.

A study of the MSR core damage frequency from PSI [2] confirmed the above claims. Many MSR concepts rely on decay heat removal outside of the active core. The interruption of salt draining process from the core is the major source of core damage frequency. Should the draining process be accidentally stopped in the middle of the process, it will be impossible to remove the decay heat from the remaining fuel in the core. Therefore, it is essential to start the investigation of the salt boiling phenomenon during accidental condition. As a first attempt to the molten salt phase change problem, the current work attempts to simulate the molten salt bubble growth using the Computational fluid dynamics (CFD) method.

Method and Assumption

The CFD simulations are carried using the PSI in-house CFD code, PSI-BOIL. PSI-BOIL is a fully three-dimensional and parallelized finite volume code for incompressible flows. The governing equations solved in the PSI-BOIL are based on the single fluid formulation. PSI-BOIL solves the momentum equation with the projection step method. For the current work, the interface tracking algorithm used in the Constrained Interpolation Profile – Conservative Semi-Lagrangian 2nd order method (CIPCSL2), it tracks the interface by solving the color advection equation at every time-steps, the details of the implemented algorithm can be referred to [3].

For FLiBe, it is used mainly as the fuel salt for the liquid fluoride thermal reactor (LFTR). The fuel channels of the LFTR are made of graphite, which has a large volumetric heat capacity. The boiling of the

salts may not be happened due to the presence of these graphite channels inside the core. The confirmation of the feasibility of boiling in the LFTR requires the input from 1D thermal hydraulics simulation that is not considered in the current study. On the contrary, the boiling of salts would happen definitely for the case of molten salt fast reactor (MSFR), in which the reactor power is much higher and the absence of graphite fuel channel.

As the objective of the current work is to test the feasibility of PSI-BOIL in performing phase change simulation for molten salt liquid. The FLiBe is used as a mock-up fluid for the MSFR (i.e., LiF-ThF₄ is used), an assumption of the FLiBe boiling is being taken. The physics of the circulating molten fuel inside the MSR is a strongly coupled problem of thermal hydraulics and neutronics. In order to only investigate the phase change behavior of the salt during these transients, decoupled problem from neutronics is considered and the fission power source term is represented by a volumetric heat source term, which distributed throughout the liquid salt. In general, the salt would evaporate before boiling take place. Nevertheless, it is assumed that the molten salt boils as if normal liquid. This can simplify the complexity of the considered problem to a two-phase single component phase change problem.

Another effect that does not considered in this study is the radiation heat transfer, which should be the case for temperature higher than 1000K.

Molten Salt Properties Evaluation

By definition, molten salt refers to the state of the salt with temperature far beyond its melting temperature. As discussed in the previous section, only the physical properties of the LiF-BeF₂ (FLiBe) is investigated. The following outlines the various correlations and methods in obtaining the required thermo-physical properties for the PSI-BOIL code. This section is mainly based on the work of creating the two-phase molten salt library in thermal hydraulics system code - RELAP/3D by the Idaho National Laboratory [4].

For PSI-BOIL simulation, one set of physical properties, (ρ , μ , c_p , λ) for both liquid and gas phase at the saturation temperature is needed, in addition to that, the specific enthalpy of vaporization (h_{iv}) and surface tension coefficient (σ) are also needed. The following outlines the approach in retrieving the FLiBe's physical properties required for the PSI-BOIL simulation.

- The Cantor (1973) correlation is used for the liquid density evaluation, and the gas density is found by the ideal gas equation assuming the low density of the salt vapor.

$$\rho_l = A_D(T - 273.15) + B_D.$$

The constant A_D and B_D can be referred to the [4].

- The liquid viscosity is evaluated by the Williams's correlation (2006),

$$\mu_l = 0.000116 \exp \left[\frac{3755}{T} \right].$$

while for the gas viscosity, the calculation is based on the Chapman-Enskog theory of gases at low density [7], i.e., the transport property of a multi-component low density gas mixture can be calculated by the weighed sum with the interaction potential of the multiple component inside the mixture.

$$\mu_v = \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\frac{X_i \mu_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n X_j \Phi_{ij}} \right],$$

where the X_i is the mole fraction of the i^{th} vapor component, Φ_{ij} is the interaction potential between the i^{th} and the j^{th} vapor component and M_i is the molecular weight of the i^{th} vapor component.

- Due to the lack of open literature for the liquid specific heat capacity, the value from Cantor (1973) is simply taken by considering that the specific heat capacity does not vary much with temperature. For gas specific heat capacity, the approach is similar to the one taken for gas viscosity.

$$c_{pv} = \sum_{i=1}^n X_i \frac{M_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n M_i} c_{pvi},$$

where the subscript i stands for the i^{th} vapour component.

- For the liquid heat conductivity, it is again based on the correlation in [6].

$$\lambda_l = 0.629697 + 0.0005T.$$

Similar approach has been taken for the gas phase as the gas viscosity and specific heat capacity,

$$\lambda_v = \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\frac{X_i \lambda_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n X_j \Phi_{ij}} \right]$$

where the λ_i can be computed by the Eucken equation for polyatomic gas at low density.

- Due to the lack of literature on experimental determination of latent heat of vaporization (h_{fg}) for molten salt, the h_{fg} and the saturation temperature (T_s) of the salt are computed by the PSI in-house Gibbs Energy Minimization Code (GEMS).
- The surface tension coefficient (σ) is required in simulating scenario involving the changing of the interface. As with other physical properties, the information in this area remains limited. The surface tension coefficient of the FLiBe is based on the experimental correlations reported in [8].

$$\sigma_{\text{FLiBe}} = 0.26921 \left[1 - \left(\frac{T}{4498.8} \right)^{1.64} \right]$$

Table 1 shows the summary of the physical properties used in the PSI-BOIL simulation.

	LiF-BeF ₂ (FLiBe)
ρ_l [kg/m ³]	1714.7
μ_l [Pa·s]	16.03×10^{-4}
c_{pl} [J/kg·K]	2386
λ_l [W/m·K]	1.34
ρ_v [kg/m ³]	0.281
μ_v [Pa·s]	8.95×10^{-5}
c_{pv} [J/kg·K]	1339
λ_v [W/m·K]	0.137
T_s [K]	1430
h_{fv} [kJ/kg]	6568
σ [N/m]	22.8×10^{-2}

Table 1: Summary of the physical properties of FLiBe under atmospheric pressure

Verification of the PSI-BOIL

Although there are plenty of studies focusing on the phase change phenomenon with PSI-BOIL, none of them implemented the volumetric heat source term within the fluid domain. Verification of the PSI-BOIL on the internally heated liquid is performed by considering the one-dimensional Stefan problem and quasi-static bubble heating problem. The fully three-dimensional form of the steady state mass and energy equations of liquid phase for both problems are included as follows for reference, as the basis for the one-dimensional solution derived in this section.

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{U} = 0$$

$$\nabla \cdot (\rho_l c_{p,l} T \mathbf{U}) = \nabla \cdot [\lambda_l \nabla(T)] + q'''$$

For both problems, fixed interface and quasi-static conditions are assumed. The physical properties such as liquid density (ρ_l), vapor density (ρ_g), specific heat capacity (h_{fg}), heat conductivity (λ_l) and the volumetric heat source (q''') are considered constant with respect to the distance from interface.

For the 1D Stefan problem, the domain is a one-dimensional domain with $x = 0$ to $x = L$. The interface is fixed at the half-way (i.e., $x = L/2$). The liquid phase is situated at the left side of the interface and vice

versa for the vapour. The set of equation can be solved in 1D Cartesian form with the three boundary conditions and one mass flux condition.

$$\frac{du}{dx} = 0,$$

$$\frac{d(\rho_l c_{p,l} T u)}{dx} = \lambda_l \frac{d^2 T}{dx^2} + q'''.$$

1. Mass transfer at the interface,

$$m'' = \rho_l u_I.$$

2. Saturation temperature condition,

$$T_I = T_s.$$

3. Far-field Neumann boundary condition,

$$\left. \frac{dT}{dx} \right|_{x=0} = 0.$$

4. Mass flux condition,

$$m'' = - \left. \frac{\lambda_l}{h_{fg}} \frac{dT}{dx} \right|_I.$$

where the subscript I and $x = 0$ stand for the interface and the boundary of the domain respectively. The general solution of the Stefan problem is then found to be,

$$T = T_s + \frac{B}{A}(x - L) + \frac{B}{A^2} \left[\exp(-Ax) - \exp(-AL) \right].$$

where the coefficient of A and B are

$$A = \left. \frac{c_p}{h_{fg}} \frac{dT}{dx} \right|_I,$$

$$B = - \frac{q'''}{\lambda_l}.$$

For the bubble-heating problem, considering a perfect symmetric molten salt bubble with a fixed radius R_B , which bathed with a pool of internally heated fluid. Due to its symmetry in both θ and ϕ directions, the steady state solution of the considered problem can be obtained by solving the one-dimensional mass and energy conservation equations in direction r . The following set of equation are similar to those of Stefan problem, it is just stated here for reference.

$$\frac{du}{dr} + \frac{2u}{r} = 0,$$

$$\frac{\rho_l c_{p,l}}{r^2} \frac{d(r^2 u T)}{dr} = \frac{\lambda_l}{r^2} \frac{d}{dr} \left(r^2 \frac{dT}{dr} \right) + q'''.$$

Similar to the Stefan problem, the current problem requires also three boundary conditions and one mass flux condition to relate the mass flux and interface temperature gradient.

1. Mass transfer due to phase change at the interface,

$$m'' = \rho_l [\dot{R} - u_l(R_B)],$$

$$\frac{m''}{\rho_l} = m'' \left(\frac{1}{\rho_v} - \frac{1}{\rho_l} \right) - u_l(R_B).$$

where, R' is the interface velocity and it is obtained by considering the change in interface position during phase change from liquid to vapor (i.e., it is referred to volumetric phase change in three-dimensional sense if m' is used instead of m'').

2. Saturation temperature condition,

$$T_I = T_s.$$

3. Far-field Neumann boundary condition,

$$\left. \frac{dT}{dx} \right|_{x=0} = 0.$$

4. Mass flux condition,

$$m'' = -\frac{\lambda_l}{h_{fg}} \left. \frac{dT}{dx} \right|_I.$$

The general solution of the bubble heating problem is then found to be,

$$T(r) = \frac{1}{2} A^2 B \exp \left[-\frac{A}{r} \right] Ei \left[\frac{A}{r} \right] + \frac{ABr}{2} + C_2 \exp \left[-\frac{A}{r} \right] + \frac{D}{A} - \frac{Br^2}{2},$$

where the coefficients are,

$$A = \frac{c_{p,l}}{h_{f,g}} \left. \frac{dT}{dr} \right|_I R_B^2 \left[\frac{\rho_l}{\rho_v} - 2 \right],$$

$$B = \frac{q'''}{3\lambda_l},$$

$$D = R_B^2 \left. \frac{dT}{dr} \right|_I \left[\frac{c_{p,l}}{h_{f,g}} \left(\frac{\rho_l}{\rho_v} - 2 \right) T_s - 1 \right] - q''' \frac{R_B^3}{3\lambda_l}.$$

The remaining constant C_2 can be found by the far-field boundary condition.

It is obvious that the general solution of both problems depends on the interface temperature gradient, which is not a known priori before solving the set of equations. Thus, the general solution of the considered problem is parametric dependence problem, depending on various parameters defined in the problem, e.g. the size of the domain, the fixed radius/length of the vapor phase.

Domain and Mesh Description

For the 1D Stefan problem, the length of the domain is L , and the interface between liquid and vapour is situated at $x = L/2$. The liquid with the volumetric heat source is located at the left side of the interface and the vapour is at the right side. There are two boundary conditions at the x direction, a wall boundary condition at the left boundary and an outlet boundary condition at the right boundary of the domain.

For the bubble-heating problem, it is a three-dimensional simulation case. The bubble is situated at the centre of the Cartesian computational domain with radius R_B . Apart from the bubble, the whole domain is the internally heated liquid with the volumetric heat source. The outlet boundary condition is applied to all the six faces of the cubic domain. The length of the cubic domain is set to be 2 mm. Three grid sizes have been used.

Table 2 shows the size of the domain and the volumetric heat source density for both problem. For both problems and the subsequent bubble growth simulation, the volumetric heat source (q''') used is 7% of the volumetric heat source in the referenced MSR channel (i.e., $1.3 \times 10^8 \text{ W} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$) [9].

	Grid A	Grid B	Grid C
1D Stefan	$150 \times 4 \times 4$	$200 \times 4 \times 4$	$250 \times 4 \times 4$
Bubble Heating	$72 \times 72 \times 72$	$96 \times 96 \times 96$	$120 \times 120 \times 120$

Table 2: The computation grid sizes for the 1D Stefan and the bubble heating problem. For the 1D Stefan problem, the computation of the volumetric phase change depends on the lateral grid spacing to compute the interface area (i.e., $L_x \times L_y$).

Temperature Comparison

For the 1D Stefan problem, the outer boundary temperature of both the analytical solution and the simulation are compared, and the result shows a high order of coherence between two. The temperature percentage error is calculated as,

$$\% \text{Error} = \left| \frac{T_{\text{Simulation}} - T_s}{T_{\text{Analytical}} - T_s} \right| \times 100\%.$$

For the bubble heating problem, note that the analytical solution derived in the previous section is in one-dimension but the PSI-BOIL's simulation is three-dimension. Besides, the domain of the analytical

solution is spherically symmetric while the computational grid of the PSI-BOIL is Cartesian which leads to discrepancy when comparing the two results. In order to perform a valid comparison, the domain of the PSI-BOIL has to be fitted with respect to the spherical domain of the analytical solution by equalling the volume of the two domains,

$$L^3 = \frac{4}{3}\pi R^3.$$

Similar to the 1D Stefan problem, the temperature percentage error is calculated as the relative error of the difference between the absolute and the saturation temperature. Noted that the outer boundary used in the analytical formula is based on the above equivalence formula (i.e., 2.5 mm). The analytical solution will thus compare to the simulation value at 2 mm from the center of the Cartesian domain.

Table 3 shows the relative temperature and the percentage error of the two problems. Figure 1 and 2 show the temperature profile comparison for both problems.

$T - T_s$ [K]	Grid A	Grid B	Grid C	Analytical	Avg. % Error
1D Stefan	0.84	0.84	0.84	0.85	1.2%
Bubble Heating	11.80	11.80	12.10	11.45	5.6%

Table 3: The relative temperature and the percentage error for the 1D Stefan and the bubble heating problem. The temperature here refers to the outer boundary for the analytical solution and the respective distance from the center for the PSI-BOIL's results.

Figure 1: Temperature profile for the 1D Stefan problem.

Figure 2: Temperature profile for the bubble heating problem. Comparing to the result of the 1D Stefan problem, the analytical solution is lower than the calculated value as it is more susceptible to the influence of the Neumann boundary condition than the PSI-BOIL domain.

Volumetric Phase Change Comparison

The magnitude of volumetric phase change (v_{pc}) allows the comparison between the numerical and the analytical value. For phase change problem, it is the most crucial parameter to be verified as it reveals the accuracy of the numerical model to simulate phase change phenomena. The volumetric phase change (v_{pc}) can be calculated as,

$$v_{pc} = \frac{\lambda_l}{h_{fg}} \frac{dT}{dr} \Big|_I \left[\frac{1}{\rho_v} - \frac{1}{\rho_l} \right] S'$$

where S' is the effective phase change area. S' is equal to $L_x \times L_y$ for 1D Stefan problem, while, $4\pi R_B^2$ for 3D bubble heating problem.

Table 4 and 5 shows the results comparison of the volumetric phase change for both problems. The result of 1D Stefan problem shows perfect agreement between the simulation and the analytical values. For the bubble-heating problem, the volumetric phase change also shows good agreement in spite of the fact that the domains are not entirely the same.

v_{pc}	Grid A	Grid B	Grid C	Analytical
1D Stefan	1.75×10^{-12}	9.86×10^{-13}	6.31×10^{-13}	$0.0395 \times (\Delta x)^2$
Bubble Heating	1.093×10^{-8}	1.084×10^{-8}	1.080×10^{-8}	1.062×10^{-8}

Table 4: The volumetric phase change (v_{pc}) of the 1D Stefan and the bubble heating problem. For the 1D Stefan problem, the computation of the volumetric phase change depends on the lateral grid spacing to compute the interface area (i.e., $L_x \times L_y$)

%Error	Grid A	Grid B	Grid C
1D Stefan	0.01%	0.001%	0%
Bubble Heating	2.91%	2.07%	1.74%

Table 5: The percentage error of the volumetric phase change (vpc) for the 1D Stefan and the bubble heating problem.

Both results for the temperature and the volumetric phase change verify the PSI-BOIL code for the use for phase change simulations with internal heat sources.

Bubble Growth Simulation

The bubble growth simulation performed in this section is the preliminary investigation for the forthcoming boiling simulation in the MSR channel during accidental scenario. Due to the LOFA and LOHS accident, the salt will remain stagnant in the MSR channel due to the loss of natural circulation. The liquid is thus heated up by the internally volumetric heat source. Upon the temperature rises up to several degree above the saturation temperature, heterogeneous nucleation will start preferably at the nucleation site within the molten salt liquid. For this preliminary investigation, only single bubble is considered. Also, the heterogeneous nucleation process is not simulated. There are two approaches to perform the bubble growth simulation, first, the module for transport equation of the color function and the buoyancy effect are activated only after 1 second simulation time in PSI-BOIL. This artificial approach could resemble the heterogeneous nucleation process, however, without the consideration of the initial bubble growth at the nucleation site. The second approach is to initialise the domain to a superheated condition at the beginning of the simulation with the consideration of the thermal boundary layer of the bubble.

A single bubble growth simulation is performed using a fully three-dimensional Cartesian grid. The initial bubble size is chosen to be 1 mm. The choice of the initial bubble size is constrained by two factors, first, the realistic nature of the bubble size and, second, the computational requirement on the number of meshes required to retrieve the correct volumetric phase change at the fluid interface. In order to reveal the effect of heat-up due to internal volumetric heat source, it is required to simulate up to the order of seconds to investigate the influence of the volumetric heat source. As the bubble rises up in the domain by the buoyancy effect, a long domain in z-axis is required to accommodate the bubble for such a long simulation time which leads to a high computational requirement.

The domain is shown as in figure 3. For the simulation, an initial bulk superheat value of 2.2K is chosen. A relatively fine mesh ($144 \times 144 \times 720$, with axial spacing of 0.139 mm) is chosen for the first case to

demonstrate the feasibility of PSI-BOIL in simulating bubble growth simulation. The real computational time is around 2.5 days on a 48 core ETH cluster Euler for a simulation time of 0.3 s.

Figure 3 : Domain of the bubble growth simulation. The vertical dimension (z direction) of the domain is 10 cm with the same lateral dimensions for x and y directions of 2 cm. The bubble with initial radius of R_b is initialized at the point $\{0,0,0\}$ at the beginning of the simulation.

Figure 4 and 5 show the color function and the temperature of the bubble growth simulation at 0 s, 0.12 s, 0.2 s and 0.28 s. The result shows the change of the interface (from spherical shape to a shape with dipped interface) due to buoyancy force is qualitatively comparable with the case of ordinary liquid, e.g. water. The result shows the feasibility to conduct phase change simulation for molten salt liquid.

Figure 4 : Color function of the bubble growth simulation. From left to right, 0 s, 0.12 s, 0.2 s and 0.28 s to the volumetric heat source. The average heatup of the domain is around 0.65K for 0.28 s

Figure 5 : Temperature of the bubble growth simulation. From left to right, 0 s, 0.12 s, 0.2 s and 0.28 s, the increase of temperature in the liquid is due to the volumetric heat source. The average heatup of the domain is around 0.65K for 0.28 s

Mesh Sensitivity Study

In addition, two simulations with different mesh sizes are performed, the coarser (120×120×600) and the finer (160×160×800) cases. Generally, the finer the mesh, the greater would be the gradient of the color function resolved at the near interface region and leading to stronger phase change at the interface. Nevertheless, there would be a converging trend of the solution when the number of grid cells near the interface is adequate to resolve the rising part of the boundary temperature profile.

	Grid A	Grid B	Grid C
Grid Size	120 × 120 × 600	144 × 144 × 720	160 × 160 × 800
Cell Size [mm]	0.167	0.138	0.125

Table 6: Grid and cell sizes for the three simulations

From figure 6 and 7, one can see that the result is converging from Grid B to Grid C. If one performs another simulation with grid index higher than Grid C, it should show a fully converged case of simulation, however, the case with 196 grid cells in lateral dimension leads to an enormous computation requirement. Another approach is to further increase the boundary thickness such that more cells can be included in the boundary region for the same cell size. It is not fully understood that how thick the thermal boundary layer of molten salt liquid should be. The choice of the boundary layer thickness in the current work is arbitrary, as there is no data in the open literature regarding to the thermal boundary layer thickness of molten salt. One could thus see that the boundary thickness is also another constraint on the grid size for a grid-independence simulation.

Figure 6: Volumetric phase change with respect to time for the three grid sizes

Figure 7: Lateral radius with respect to time for the three grid sizes

Conclusion

The result of this preliminary investigation proves the capability of PSI-BOIL to simulate phase change in an internally heated fluid. Further investigation can be performed at simulating a representative MSR channel to quantify the dynamics of the system and characterize the void distribution during the accidental scenario.

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